

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Effects of vegetation density on the diversity of lizards in an area of the Brazilian Cerrado

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Figure S1. Phylogenetic tree of lizard species sampled with pitfall traps at the Santa Bárbara Ecological Station. Only species with more than five individuals sampled are included. Colors represent each family. Blue: Gymnophthalmidae; Gold: Teiidae; Orange: Anolidae; Purple: Scincidae.

Figure S2. Shepard plot (or stress plot) to observe the goodness of fit of the data into the NMDS analysis.

Figure S3. Half-normal plots with Simulation Envelopes of the best fitted generalized linear models showing the predicted effect of A – NDVI (300 m buffer) on lizard richness; B– NDVI (300 m buffer) on lizard abundance.

Figure S4. Forest plot illustrating 95% CI of models of taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional diversity, and LCBD in different scales.

Error bar colors represent model's slope, positive (blue) or negative (red).